

NUTRITIONAL AND ANTINUTRITIONAL VALUES OF BOJER (*Argyreia nervosa*) SEEDS

Fowomola, M. A.

Science Technology Department, School of Applied Sciences and Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Kwara State. E-mail: moshoodfowomola@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The proximate composition, mineral, amino acid, vitamin and antinutrient contents of Bojer (*Argyreia nervosa*) seeds were investigated. The results of the proximate analysis show that bojer seed is very rich in crude protein ($22.47 \pm 1.12\%$), lipid ($13.67 \pm 0.68\%$), crude fibre ($15.72 \pm 0.79\%$), ash ($3.68 \pm 0.18\%$), carbohydrate ($44.46 \pm 2.22\%$) and energy content (390.75 ± 19.48 KJ/100g). The results also indicated that bojer seed contains Na (23.11 mg/100), Mg (4.96 mg/100), Fe (16.22 mg/100), Zn (1.24 mg/100), Ca (5.77 mg/100), Cu (0.14 mg/100), K (30.25 mg/100) and Mn (33.29 mg/100). Amino acid analysis revealed that bojer seed contains mainly aspartate (4.49 g/ 100g protein), lysine (4.48 g/ 100g protein), leucine (5.18 g/ 100g protein), glutamate (7.66 g/ 100g protein) and histidine (0.65 g/ 100g protein). The vitamin analysis showed that bojer contained 1764.72 ± 2.12 (IU) vitamin A, 0.30 ± 0.03 mg/100g vitamin E, 0.082 ± 0.02 mg/100g Vitamin K, 0.038 ± 0.03 mg/100g Vitamin B1, 0.04 ± 0 mg/100g, Vitamin B2, 0.12 ± 0 mg/100g, Vitamin B6, 0.125 ± 0.01 mg/100g, Vitamin B12 and 4.66 ± 0.02 mg/100g Vitamin C. Results of antinutrient analysis show that bojer seed contains alkaloid (2.01 ± 0.10 mg/100g), tannins (1.21 ± 0.06 mg/100g), phytate (1.52 ± 0.08 mg/100g), cyanogenic glycoside (0.043 ± 0.01 mg/100g), and saponin (0.63 ± 0.03 mg/100g). Trypsin inhibitor activity was found to be ($11.84 \pm .59$ TIU/mg protein). The results showed that bojer seed is not only rich in caloric level but also low in concentrations of antinutritional factors.

KEYWORDS antinutritional, *argyreia nervosa*, bojer, trypsin inhibitor.

INTRODUCTION

Protein-energy malnutrition (PEM), remains the most common serious nutritional problem in almost all countries of Asia, Africa, Latin America and the Near East. This may be attributed to war, political instability and poverty. In addition, high rates of population growth and current patterns of population dispersion threaten world health and welfare. For instant, in Nigeria where the population is over 120,000,000, most people can not afford to buy conventional protein sources (such as meat, fish, egg, chicken and milk) as a result of the poor economic. The search for alternative sources of foods which will be readily available to all is inevitable.

Several workers, such as Umoh *et. al.*, (1980) and Mba (1980) had highlighted a good number of lesser known animal foods such as clam, periwinkle and land snail, whose consumption was limited to a small population due to lack of adequate information about their nutritional potentials. In addition, Aletor and Aladetimi (1989) provided information on the nutritional potentials of some locally available under-utilized leguminous plant seeds. Furthermore, Fowomola and Akidahunsi (2007) reported on the nutritional quality of sandbox tree, an under-utilized plant in Nigeria.

Argyreia nervosa, otherwise known as Bojer, Hawaiian baby wood rose, Elephant creeper and woolly Morning Glory belongs to the family *Convolvulaceae*. It originated from the Indian subcontinent and it introduced to numerous areas worldwide, including Hawaii, Africa and Caribbean. Presently, the plant is cultivated in all the tropical regions as an ornamental tree and as a narcotic (amazingnature, 2005). This plant has large heart-shaped foliage (hairy from the bottom and 30cm across), violet coloured funnel-shaped flowers and round fruits that contain one to four seeds. The vine can reach 10 meters in height and the plant can be propagated vegetatively (by cutting), by seeds in humid soil at temperatures of 20-25° C.

The seeds of *A. nervosa* have hallucinogenic properties and are used as “cheap buzz”, an alternative to alcohol in Hawaii, Haiti and Puerto Rico. Three to eight seeds may produce psychedelic effects comparative to Lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD). The experience usually reported include extreme lassitude, changes in visual and auditory perception, emotional disturbances, nausea, papillary dilation, tremor, increase in blood pressure and body temperature. In addition, the seed can cause uterine contractions, which may lead to miscarriage in a pregnant woman if she consumes it. However, with appropriate dosage and supervision, the effects can be used to aid child birth (amazingnature, 2005). The leaves and roots of *A. nervosa* which are not psychoactive are used as antiseptic and anti-inflammatory drugs in India.

Phytochemical analysis has revealed that the seeds contain 0.3 to 1 % ergot-alkaloids by weight. These include Ergine (d-Lysergic acid amide) and its derivatives such as ergometrine. The hallucinogenic or psychedelic effects experienced after consumption of *A. nervosa* seeds are usually attributed to Ergine (d-Lysergic acid amide) and its derivatives (amazingnature, 2005). The “furry” outer skin of the seeds contains cyanogenic glycosides, the ingestion of which is the likely cause of nausea reported by those who have eaten the seeds. The main body of the plant contains small amount of strychnine, a potent toxin, but its presence is negligible in the seeds (amazingnature, 2005). However there is scarcity of information on the nutritional and antinutritional factors in bojer (*argyreia nervosa*) seeds which can serve as a guide for the possible utilisation of bojer seeds by animal/ human feed manufacturers, public health authorities and other food regulatory bodies. Therefore, the present work is aimed to provide this information.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Collection of Samples

Bojer seeds were collected from a mechanical workshop, Tipper Garage, Offa in Kwara State, Nigeria, identified and authenticated by a botanist at Department of Science Technology, School of Applied Sciences and Technology, Federal Polytechnic Offa Kwara State, Nigeria.

All Analytical grade reagents used for chemical analysis were supplied by BDH Ltd., Poole, UK.

Methods

Sample Treatment

The seeds were hulled from their coats, air – dried in the laboratory for two weeks, ground to a mesh size of 1 mm (using Laboratory pestle and Mortar) and kept in air-tight sterilised containers for analysis.

Proximate Analysis

Crude protein, Lipid, Ash, Crude fibre, Carbohydrate and energy contents of Bojer seed were determined by using the methods described by Horwitz (1980), Pearson (1973), Foster and Leslie (1971), Norman and Waddington (1989) and Okoye (1992), respectively.

Determination of minerals

Preparation of sample

Sample (2g) was ashed at 500°C to a constant weight. 15ml of 20% (v/v) nitric acid solution was added to the crucible to break up the ash. This was boiled and filtered through No.43 Whatman filter paper. The residue and the paper were washed 3 times with deionised water into a standard 100ml volumetric flask and then diluted to 100ml with deionised water.

Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) (Pye Unicam Sp 9 AAS) was used for the determination of Calcium, Copper, Manganese, Zinc, Magnesium and Iron as described by Perkin-Elmer (1982) while Sodium and Potassium were determined by using flame spectrophotometer.

Amino acid profile

The amino acid profile in the sample was determined using method described by Spackman *et al.*, (1958). The sample was dried to constant weight, defatted, hydrolyzed, evaporated in a rotary evaporator and then loaded into the Technicon Sequential Multisample amino acid analyzer (TSM) for analysis.

Determination of Vitamins

Vitamins were determined using the methods described by Association of Vitamin Chemists (1987).

Determination of Antinutrients

The contents of cyanide, tannin, alkaloid, oxalate, saponin and trypsin inhibitor activity in bojer seed were determined according to the methods described by Harborne (1998), Makkar *et al.*, (1993), Harbone (1973), Ukpabi and Ejidoh (1989), Fenwick and Oakenful (1983) and Kakade *et al.*, (1974) respectively.

Statistical analysis: Results of Proximate analysis, Vitamins and antinutrients were presented as mean \pm SD of three determinations.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the proximate composition and energy content of bojer seed. The results indicated that bojer seed is very rich in Carbohydrate (44.46 ± 2.22 %) while the protein content is 22.47 ± 1.12 %, Lipid 13.67 ± 0.68 % and crude fibre 15.72 ± 0.79 %. The energy content is 390.75 ± 19.48 KJ/100g. Table 2 depicts the concentrations of mineral assayed in bojer seed. The results showed that bojer seed contains 23.11(mg/100) Na, 3.4(mg/100) K, 5.77 (mg/100)Ca,4.96(mg/100) Mg, 16.22(mg/100) Fe and 1.24 (mg/100) Zn,0.14(mg/100) Cu and 33.29(mg/100) Mn. The amino acid profile of bojer seed is as presented in Table 3 . The results revealed that bojer seed is very rich in glutamate (7.66g/100g of protein) while cysteine (0.78g/100g of protein) has the lowest value. Among the essential amino acids, arginine has the highest value (5.97g/100g of protein). This is followed by leucine which has the value of 5.18 g/100g of protein. Table 4 shows the vitamins contents (mg/100g) of bojer (*argyreia nervosa*) seeds. The results showed that bojer contained 1764.72 \pm 2.12 (IU) vitamin A, 0.30 \pm 0.03 mg/100g vitamin E, 0.082 \pm 0.02 mg/100g Vitamin K, 0.038 \pm 0.03 mg/100g Vitamin B1, 0.04 \pm 0 mg/100g, Vitamin B2, 0.12 \pm 0 mg/100g, Vitamin B6, 0.125 \pm 0.01 mg/100g, Vitamin B12 and 4.66 \pm 0.02 mg/100g Vitamin C. Table 5 depicts the antinutrients contents of bojer seed. The results revealed that trypsin inhibitor has the highest value (11.84 \pm 0.59TIU/mg) followed by alkaloid (2.01 \pm 0.01mg/100g) while cyanide has the lowest value (0.043 \pm 0.01mg/100g).

DISCUSSION

The results of proximate analysis showed that bojer seed is a nutritionally promising seed because of its high levels of oil, protein and carbohydrate. It is more nutritious when compared with sweet yellow maize(Cortéz, and Wild-Altamirano, 1972). High level of crude fibre in bojer seed is of benefit to mankind. It has been reported that fruits containing high level of crude fibre are able to control glycaemia by reducing the absorption of glucose in the intestine (Anderson *et al.*, 1988). In addition, insoluble fibre has been found to be helpful in the treatment and prevention of constipation, haemorrhoids, diverticulosis, high blood cholesterol levels, the risk of coronary heart disease and colon cancer (Slavin, 1990).

The results of the amino acid analysis showed that bojer seed is very rich in some essential amino acids that are needed for normal functioning of the body. The amino acid requirements for infants and 10–12-year-old children have been reported to be 31 mg/kg/day for isoleucine, 64 mg/kg/day for lysine, 27 mg/kg/day for sulfur amino acids, 37 mg/kg/day for threonine and 14 mg/kg/day for tryptophan (Pineda *et al.*,1981). There are also evidences that histidine is an essential amino acid for adults and its dietary requirement in both normal and uremic men has been reported to be between 8 and 12 mg/kg/day (Giordano *et al.*, 1972, Bergstrom *et al.*, 1970 and Kopple *et al.*, 1975) .

The results of mineral assay showed that bojer seed is very rich in sodium and manganese. Sodium plays a vital role in active transport across the cell membrane and is also required for maintenance of osmotic balance (Ann, 2010) while manganese serves as a coenzyme for Superoxide Dismutase (Jefferson

et.al.,2009). The presence of antioxidant vitamins such as vitamin C, E and A suggests that bojer seed could be used as an alternative source of these vitamins. Antioxidant vitamins have been reported to reduce oxidative processes which are known to be vital in the initiation of arthrosclerosis Steinberg, *et. al.* (1989). The results of antinutrient analysis showed that bojer seed contained some secondary metabolites which may cause problems if consume raw. However, they are very low in concentration when compared with those of maize (Hassan *et. al.*, 2005). These included tannins which are aromatic compounds containing phenolic groups. They interact with salivary proteins and glycoproteins in the mouth and render the tissues astringent to taste (Howes, 1953). Astringency gives tannin the medicinal value in preventing diarrhoea and dysentery and for controlling haemorrhage (Sollman, 1957; Jones, 1965). Furthermore, tannins protect plant against dehydration, rotting, damage by animals and pathogens. When they are polymerised, insoluble protective barrier is formed which prevents microbial attack (Stumpf and Conn, 1981). Therefore they can be applied to wounds as protective coating. Bichel and Bach (1968) reported that the symptoms of continued intake of tannin include gastritis as well as irritation and edema of the intestine. Glick and Joslyn (1970) also reported that feeding 0.5% of tannic acid decreased nitrogen retention and caused 5% mortality in rats. Tannins are known to bind strongly to proteins *in vitro* and form a compound called tannin-protein complex (T-PC). The complexes are quite resistant to degradation by digestive enzymes, thereby interfering with nitrogen balance *in vivo* (Feeny,1976; Mcleod, 1974; Rhoades, and Cates, 1976).

In addition, the work of Chung *et.al.*, (1998) revealed that tannins have anticarcinogenic and antimutagenic potentials, which is important in protecting cellular oxidative damage, including lipid peroxidation in human.

Savage *et.al.*, (1964) reported that phytate depressed the growth of chicks fed with phytate – casein diet by forming complex with zinc thereby making the later unavailable. Omosaiye and Cheryan (1979) also reported that phytate formed complex with protein by the actions of cations, usually calcium, zinc or magnesium which act as a bridge between the negatively charged protein carboxyl groups and former. The report of Chen *et.al.*, (1934), shown that the minimum lethal dose of hydrogen cyanide taken by man through mouth to be between 0.5mg and 3.5mg/kg body weight. The symptoms of hydrogen cyanide including peripheral numbness, light-headedness, mental confusion, stupor, cyanosis and convulsion were reported by Halstrom and Moiler (1945). Oxalate forms complex with calcium thereby making it unavailable when fed to animals and more so high oxalate diets can increase the risk of renal calcium absorption (Osagie and Eka, 1998). Saponins have characteristic bitter taste, foaming properties and haemolytic effect on red blood cells (Osagie and Eka, 1998). Some alkaloids for example potato alkaloid (solanine) cause gastrointestinal upsets and neurological disorders, especially when taken in excess of 20mg/100g sample (Osagie and Eka, 1998). Trypsin inhibitors are low molecular weight proteins which form complexes with trypsin thereby reducing its proteolytic activity which in turn reduces the availability of amino acids which eventually lead to reduced growth and pancreatic enlargement (Leiner, 1989).

CONCLUSION

The present study has shown that bojer seeds are not only rich in caloric level but also low in concentrations of antinutritional factors and could serve as a guide for the possible utilisation of bojer seeds by animal feed manufacturers, public health authorities and other food regulatory bodies.

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Table1. Proximate composition of bojer seeds

Composition	% (Dry Weight)
Energy content	390.75±19.48KJ/100g
Carbohydrate	44.46± 2.22
Crude Protein	22.47±1.12
Crude fibre	15.72± 0.79
Lipid	13.67± 0.68
Ash	3.68± 0.18

Each value is a mean of three determinations. [mean ± SD]

Table2. some mineral contents of bojer seeds

Mineral	Composition (mg/100g Dry Weight)
Mn	33.29
Na	23.11
Fe	16.22
K	3.4
Ca	5.77
Mg	4.96
Zn	1.24
Cu	0.14

Table 3. Amino acid profile (g/100g Dry Weight) of bojer seeds

Amino acid	quantity	Amino acid	quantity
Glutamate	7.66	Threonine	2.94
Arginine	5.97	Serine	2.86
Leucine	5.18	Isoleucine	2.80
Aspartate	4.49	Valine	2.38
Lysine	4.48	Proline	2.36
Alanine	4.13	Tyrosine	2.21
Phenylalanine	3.77	Methionine	1.32
Glycine	3.16	Cysteine	0.78
Histidine	0.65		

Table 4. Vitamins contents (mg\100g Dry Weight) of bojer seeds

Vitamins	Amount (mg\100g)
A	764.72±2.12 (IU)
C	4.66±0.02
E	0.30±0.03
B ₁₂	0.125±0.01
B ₆	0.12±0
K	0.082±0.02
B ₂	0.04±0
B ₁	0.038±0.03

Each value is a mean of three determinations [mean ± SD].

Table 5. Antinutrients content (mg/100g) of bojer seeds

Trypsin (TIU/mg)	alkaloid	phytate	oxalate	tannins	saponin	cyanide
11.84±0.59	2.01±0.01	1.52±0.08	1.41±0.07	1.21±0.06	0.613±0.03	0.043±0.01

Each value is a mean of three determinations [mean ± SD].

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